

FunGlass
centre for functional and
surface functionalized glass

Book of Abstracts

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FunGlass School 2024/2

Book of Abstracts

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Influence of Al doping on structural and optical properties of sol-gel derived ZnO thin films

Malihe Ghaffari¹, Lothar Wondraczek^{2,3}, Dusan Galusek^{1,4}, Jose J. Velazquez¹
Orhan Sisman¹

¹ FunGlass Center, TnUAD, 91150 Trencin, Slovakia, malihe.ghaffari@tnuni.sk

² Otto Schott Institute of Materials Research, FSU Jena, 07743 Jena, Germany

³ Center for Energy and Environmental Chemistry, FSU Jena, 07737 Jena, Germany,

⁴ Joint Glass Center of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChPT STU, 91150 Trencin, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Transparent conductive oxides (TCOs) have been used in various applications due to their both transparent and conductive properties. ZnO-based transparent conductive films; like aluminum doped zinc oxide (AZO) (and gallium doped zinc oxide (GZO) seem to be a good alternative instead of ITO due to worldwide scarcity of In. In this study, we investigated the sol-gel derived AZO thin films on glass substrates derived by dip-coating technique. Zinc acetate dihydrate, ethanol, and diethanolamine were used as precursors, solvent, and stabilizer, respectively. 2 and 4 and 6 mol% of Aluminum nitrate nonahydrate was added as source of Al³⁺ dopant. The obtained thin layers were annealed under controlled conditions. SEM images confirmed the formation of homogenous films with a particle size of ~35 nm. XRD results confirmed the formation of hexagonal wurtzite crystal structure of ZnO in the films whereas the Al³⁺ doping leads to the reduction of the crystallite size; from 23.5 nm (bare ZnO) to 10.8 nm with 6 mol% AZO film. The micro strain and dislocation density values of ZnO film increased from 0.50-1.08 % and 1.81-8.57 nm⁻² for bare and 6 mol% Al³⁺ doped thin films, respectively. The band gap energy of bare ZnO was estimated as 3.29 eV. There were shifts in the bandgap energies of AZO films proportional to Al³⁺ concentration due to Burstein-Moss Effect around 0.4 eV. Moreover, XPS analysis revealed the presence of Al³⁺ and the doping induced small shifts to higher binding energies in core level Zn 2p and O1s peaks. These preliminary results demonstrate the successful doping of Al³⁺ in ZnO and will help to explore the changes in the electrical properties and gas sensing properties of analyzed films.

Keywords: ZnO, AZO, sol-gel, dip coating.

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NiMo Oxide-Ti₃C₂ MXene nanocomposite for oxygen evolution reaction (OER)

Mir Saeed Sajjadi^{1,2}, Aline Emerenciano², Michelle P. Browne²

¹Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

²Helmholtz Young Investigator Group Electrocatalysis: Synthesis to Devices, Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie, Berlin, Germany

(E-mail: mir.sajjadi@tuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

The global energy landscape is transforming significantly, and sustainable and environmentally friendly energy production methods are urgently needed [1]. This research focused on developing an innovative NiMoO₄/Ti₃C₂ MXene nanocomposite for green hydrogen production through electrochemical water splitting. Current hydrogen production primarily relies on fossil fuel reforming, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions. Electrochemical water splitting offers a promising alternative but is hampered by high overpotential and inefficient reaction kinetics. The project aimed to address these challenges by creating a novel nanocomposite that combines the electrocatalytic properties of NiMoO₄ [2] with the high surface area and conductivity of Ti₃C₂ MXene [3]. Key objectives of this project include optimizing the Ni/Mo ratio and the amount of Ti₃C₂ in the composite, characterizing the morphological and electronic properties of the prepared samples, and evaluating their electrocatalytic performance for oxygen evolution reaction (OER) in an alkaline environment. Comprehensive characterization techniques, including scanning electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, and operando Raman spectroscopy, have been employed to analyze the nanocomposite's structure and composition. Electrochemical testing like linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) and chronopotentiometry (CP) assessed the catalyst's efficiency, stability, and reaction mechanisms.

Keywords: Electrochemical water splitting; Oxygen evolution reaction (OER); Ti₃C₂ MXene; NiMo oxide; Electrocatalysis.

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Tailoring Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles via the Sol-Gel Method for Enhanced Bioactivity and Drug Delivery

**Daniela Jaramillo Raquejo¹, Fatih Kurtuldu¹, Dušan Galusek^{1,2},
Aldo R. Boccaccini³ and Martin Michálek¹**

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

² Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

³ Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Material Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

Corresponding author: daniela.jaramillo@muni.sk

ABSTRACT

The sol-gel synthesis method enables the production of mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNs) with a high specific surface area and pore volume, facilitating enhanced drug loading capacity. In this work, we focused on the synthesis of silica nanoparticles (SNs) using the sol-gel and by varying the concentrations of structure-directing agents, we were able to modulate the size and pore characteristics of the resulting nanoparticles. To assess the morphology of the synthesized nanoparticles, we employed both BET (Brunauer-Emmett-Teller) surface area analysis and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). These techniques provided insights into the structural features and pore characteristics of the particles, which are crucial for evaluating their suitability for the intended applications. Three distinct morphologies of mesoporous silica nanoparticles were synthesized, with the sample exhibiting dendritic morphology and highest pore volume (2.519 m³/g) selected for its promising drug and biomolecule loading potential. The focus on achieving the optimal dendritic morphology ensures that the system can accommodate the incorporation of bioactive elements such as biomolecules or drugs in the most efficient manner. These nanoparticles were subsequently impregnated with calcium to produce dendritic mesoporous bioglass nanoparticles (DMBGNs). Four different compositions of mesoporous bioglass nanoparticles were produced, with the composition containing the highest calcium content (15.9 ± 0.5) chosen to facilitate partial calcium substitution during subsequent bismuth impregnation. This approach aims to optimize the functionality of the composite for bone tissue engineering applications.

Keywords: bioglass nanoparticles, dendritic mesoporous nanoparticles, silica nanoparticles, sol-gel method, surface properties.

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The morphological effect of bioactive glass on polymer/BG composite scaffolds for tissue regeneration

E. Varlik^{1,3*}, L. Viviant^{2,3}, F. Kurtuldu^{1,3}, Q. Nawaz³, S. Chen¹, D. Galusek^{1,4}, J. Kraxner¹, M. Michálek¹, and A. R. Boccaccini³

¹Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass - FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

²Ensil-Ensci, Industrial Ceramics Department, 16 Rue Atlantis, 87280 Limoges, France

³Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

⁴Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia
(*E-mail: ertugrul.varlik@tuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of flame-spheroidized bioactive glass microspheres (BGMs) on poly(lactic acid) (PLA) composite filaments and scaffolds aimed at tissue regeneration applications. Cubic scaffolds were fabricated via fused deposition modeling (FDM) 3D printing, enabling precise structural control. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed an even distribution of BGMs within the polymer matrix, indicating good integration with PLA. Filaments containing BGMs demonstrated higher tensile strength than those with irregularly shaped bioactive glass particles. Additionally, PLA/BGM scaffolds exhibited superior compressive strength, showing higher stress at 30% strain compared to other scaffold types. After seven days of incubation with MG-63 cells, PLA/BGM scaffolds displayed the highest cell viability. These findings suggest that incorporating BGMs into PLA filaments and scaffolds enhances mechanical properties and supports biological activity, highlighting their potential for bone regeneration applications.

Keywords: Bioactive glass microspheres, Bone tissue engineering, Fused deposition modeling, Poly(lactic) acid

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Alkali-Activated Materials based on Volcanic Ash and Waste Glass: sustainable and alternative geomaterials from waste to resource

**Zafarana S. E.¹, Scanferla P.², Finocchiaro C.¹, Barone G.¹, Mazzoleni P.¹, Dušan Galusek^{2,3},
Kraxner J.²**

¹ Department of Biological, Geological and Environmental Sciences, University of Catania, Italy
(E-mail: sabrina.zafarana@phd.unict.it)

² FunGlass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, Slovakia

³ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChFT STU, Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

In response to increasing ecological and climate challenges, there is a shift towards minimizing the environmental impact of the construction industry. As a result, developing alternative materials to Portland Cement has become crucial. This study investigates the potential of using waste materials such as nonrecyclable glass from Johns Manville company (E-fiber glass producer, Slovakia) and volcanic ash from Mt. Etna (Italy) through an alkaline activation process. Waste glass, which amounts to an annual production of about 200 tons, poses a significant environmental challenge. Similarly, volcanic ash from Mt. Etna is classified as solid municipal waste and disposed of in landfills if not used in a safe and innovative process. Previous research has demonstrated that similar materials can be effectively used in producing alkali-activated materials (AAMs) with promising and advanced properties. In particular, this work aims to produce AA-pastes using mixtures of volcanic ash and waste glass from glass fibers in a borosilicate system as precursors, with two mix ratios (40-60 wt.% and 20-80 wt.% of waste glass and volcanic ash, respectively) activated with 7M and 9M potassium hydroxide solution and cured at 60°C for 4 days. A multidisciplinary approach was performed, including a feasibility study to assess the material's resistance to boiling water for up to three hours; XRD to investigate the differences in the crystalline phases between raw materials and the final obtained specimens; FT-IR and SEM-EDX analysis to evaluate the gel formation and the surface morphology; Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) was used to investigate the potential for heavy metal release; compressive strength tests and helium pycnometer measures to quantify and evaluate the influence on the mechanical properties of the different reactants involved in each mix design related to the porosity of the samples. The results have shown that all formulations studied are feasible, with enhanced mechanical performance for the mixtures with the lowest volcanic ash content for both molarities of KOH, achieving values of approximately 20 MPa. Porosity decreased with the increase of alkali concentration, from approximately 25% for 7M to 21% for 9M. Carbonated and hydrated phases were identified from both XRD and FT-IR analysis, a sign that the reaction among glass, ash, and alkali took place to form a stable gel. Grains of glass and ash are visibly embedded into an Al-Si-Ca matrix, as highlighted by SEM and EDX. These findings support the potential application of these mixtures in additive manufacturing processes for producing construction elements in more complex designs primarily from inorganic waste-based materials.

Keywords: mixed alkali-activation; volcanic ash; waste glass.

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Side-emitting fibers: Targeted light scattering in optical fibers

**Aaron Reupert¹, Maximilian Heck², Stefan Nolte², Ismael Chiamenti³, Maria Chernysheva³,
Lothar Wondraczek¹**

¹Otto Schott Institute of Materials Research, Friedrich Schiller University Frauenhofer Straße 6, D-07743 Jena, Germany

(E-mail: aaron.reupert@uni-jena.de)

²Institute of Applied Physics, Friedrich Schiller University Albert-Einstein-Straße 15, D-07745 Jena, Germany

³Institut für Photonische Technologien Albert-Einstein-Straße 9, D-07745 Jena, Germany

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the transformation of commercial optical fibers into advanced line-shaped light sources with controllable emission characteristics through femtosecond laser-written microstructures and fiber Bragg gratings (FBGs). These light-scattering fibers, or side-emitting fibers, hold significant promise in endoscopic photo-medicine, particularly for interstitial phototherapy in cancer treatment and epilepsy management. Current commercially available light-diffusing fibers face two major limitations: they typically exhibit exponentially decaying emission profiles and predominantly forward-directed scattering, restricting their usefulness in applications requiring homogeneous or angular-selective illumination. We address these challenges by demonstrating that femtosecond-laser-induced refractive index modifications and FBGs can be employed to construct arbitrary longitudinal and angular light emission profiles from commercial optical fibers. This approach enables precise control over both the spatial distribution and directionality of emitted light, advancing the development of sophisticated optical fiber-based light sources for medical and technological applications.

Keywords: femtosecond laser micromachining, fiber bragg gratings (FBGs), side-emitting fibers, interstitial phototherapy, controlled light emission profiles

Glass Fertilizer

Franziska Scheffler¹, Lothar Wondraczek¹

¹Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Otto Schott Institute of Materials Research (OSIM), Laboratory of Glass Sciences, CEECII Lessingstraße 12-14, 07743 Jena, Germany

(E-mail: franzi.scheffler@uni-jena.de)

ABSTRACT

Enhancing the efficiency of food production while attenuating the adverse environmental effects of agriculture, such as soil degradation, water pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions, is of paramount importance. Sustainable glass fertilizer plays a crucial role in this regard by dissolving congruently and releasing nutrients at a controlled and chemically defined slow rate. This fertilizer consists of plant-available macroelements (P, K, Mg, Ca) and essential microelements, with adaptable quantities tailored to the specific needs of individual plants and the unique characteristics of the soil.

Our research involved conducting greenhouse experiments using different soil media containing varied glass fertilizer chemistries. We examined the dissolution kinetics under controlled conditions and studied the direct interaction between the fertilizer and plants. Notably, crimson clover roots exhibited an affinity for attaching to the glass particles and manipulate the glass dissolution bio-chemically. These investigations bridge the gap between laboratory-scale dissolution experiments and the practical application of glass fertilizer on a larger scale.

Keywords: glass fertilizer, controlled nutrient release, dissolution kinetics, soil-plant interaction

Facile fabrication of a bioactive Si-Ca MBG-based coating for zirconia implants

Zulema Vargas-Osorio¹, Martina Vitázková¹, Aleksandra Nowicka¹, Kai Zheng², Dušan Galusek^{1,3} and Martin Michálek¹

¹Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass (FunGlass), Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia.

²Jiangsu Province Engineering Research Center of Stomatological Translational Medicine, Nanjing Medical University, 210029, Nanjing, China.

³Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

In recent years, zirconia has proven to be a suitable material for dental applications. Yttria-stabilized tetragonal zirconia polycrystals (Y-TZP) are particularly used in odontology due to their exceptional mechanical properties, including high fracture toughness and flexural strength, as well as corrosion and wear resistance. In addition, zirconia has excellent aesthetics that make it visually appealing by resembling the colour of natural teeth. The use of zirconia has also demonstrated lower bacterial adhesion and plaque formation compared to titanium implants. Despite all their advantageous features, further studies are needed to evaluate their success as long-term implants due to their lack of bioactivity and low osseointegration. A few research has been done to improve the surface properties of zirconia and therefore enhance its biological response. Sandblasting and acid etching are among the most commonly used methods. In this sense, mesoporous bioactive glasses (MBGs) can be an attractive option for coating zirconia surfaces, as they have evidenced to be highly biocompatible and bioactive, as well as promoting the formation of the pulp-dentin complex. Therefore, the development of a bioactive coating on zirconia implants previously treated with atmospheric plasma can be a promising and innovative candidate in dentistry.

The goal of this work is to optimize the parameters for creating a highly porous and uniform coating of (SiO₂-CaO binary system) MBG on zirconia implants in a simple and consistent manner. A suspension of MBG nanoparticles was used to investigate the factors influencing the dip coating process. These factors include immersion speed, withdrawal speed, number of dips, and the duration of implant submersion and exposure to the dispersion. The second step involved modifying the surface of the zirconia implant to enhance the attachment of particles, while the final step focused on stabilising and optimising the dispersion of MBG particles. By utilizing SEM, EDS, FTIR, and confocal microscopy, the homogeneity of the MBG coating across the zirconia surface was verified. The original structure and characteristics of the MBG nanoparticles were preserved, resulting in a hierarchically porous coating with pores ranging from microns to nanometers. The coating exhibited surface roughness represented by S_a (arithmetic mean height) and S_q (squared mean height) values of $1.0 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ and $1.2 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, respectively.

Keywords: Bioactive coatings, Dental applications, Dip coating, Mesoporous bioactive glasses, Zirconia implants.

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1393B3 Borate-based Bioactive Glass Scaffolds for Bone Regeneration Fabricated by Additive Manufacturing Based on Vat Photopolymerization

S. Chen¹, A. A. Altun², S. Nohut², M. Schwentenwein², D. Galusek^{1,3}, M. Michálek¹

¹ FunGlass, A. Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, Trenčín, 911 50, Slovakia
(E-mail: si.chen@tnuni.sk)

² Lithoz GmbH, Mollardgasse 85A/2/64-69, Vienna, 1060, Austria

³ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnU AD and FChFT STU, TnU AD, Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

By mimicking the hierarchical pore system of natural bone, it is possible to influence the differentiation and signalling expression of bone-related cells, thereby modulating the bone regeneration process. A bespoke high-resolution digital light processing (DLP) additive manufacturing (AM) machine for ceramics based on vat photopolymerisation (VPP), is used due to its capability of printing intricate porous structures that mimic the architecture of natural bone. As a well-established material for bone regeneration, bioactive glasses (BGs) are highly desirable for constructing bone regeneration scaffolds using AM techniques. In these approaches, organic binders are used to shape the raw material powder. Eventually, the binder is removed by debinding process, and the raw material powder is fused into an integrated unit. In this study, 1393B3 borate BGs were selected for printing bioactive glass scaffolds via VPP due to their ability to densify at temperatures ~ 600°C and retention of the amorphous state. Zinc-doped bioactive glass nanoparticles (NPs) were incorporated into the feedstock to endow the scaffolds with potential antimicrobial features and improve cell-scaffold adhesion/interaction via the enhanced surface area. SEM microstructure analysis of the scaffold cross sections shows that after sintering, the raw material particles are almost completely fused, while XRD diffraction patterns reveal that the materials constituting the scaffolds are still in an amorphous state. XRD analysis revealed the formation of the hydroxyapatite phase after a 14-day immersion of the scaffolds in SBF.

Keywords: borate bioactive glass, digital light processing, gyroid, additive manufacturing

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Structural and in-vitro characterization of RadioBiocoats: radiopaque thermally sprayed coatings

G. Clavijo-Mejía¹, L. Youssef², Q. Nawaz³, M. Arango³, I. Unalan³, F. Kurtuldu¹, M. Michálek¹, D. Galusek^{1,4} and A. R. Boccaccini³

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Duubcek University of Trencín, Studentská 2, 911 50, Trencín, Slovakia
german.clavijo@tuni.sk

²Institute of Research for Ceramics–IRCER, UMR 7315, CNRS, Centre Européen de la Ceramique (CEC),
Université de Limoges, 12 Rue Atlantis, 87068, Limoges, Cedex, France

³Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Material Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg,
91058, Erlangen, Germany

⁴Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChPT STU, Studentská 2, 911 50, Trencín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Bioactive glasses (BG) are being widely used as feedstock material to improve the surface biocompatibility of medical devices. An example of this is the functionalization of metallic implant surfaces to improve their osteointegration when used in musculoskeletal functions. The BG amorphous nature and fabrication through melt and quench of the precursors make this biomaterial an easy candidate to modify its applications based on the tunable glass composition. Such applications are diverse and cover a wide range of aims. Bismuth (Bi) addition on silicate and borate BG has shown to be an interesting modification to improve the reduced contrast in medical imaging (radiopacity) of its surface compared to non-coated metallic surfaces.

RadioBiocoats is an initiative supported by the Slovak Research Council (VAIA) that seeks to obtain radiopaque bioactive glass coatings with proper biocompatibility and bioactivity. For this, a deep analysis of the fabrication of Bi-containing BG feedstock powder is performed as a first stage. The results lead to finding the proper Bi content to improve the BG powder radiopacity keeping the glass biocompatibility. Afterward, three of the most common technologies to be used in surface functionalization named atmospheric plasma spray (APS), sol-gel dip coating (SGDP), and electrophoretic deposition (EPD) are used under a design of experiments (DoE) to determine the coating deposition parameters of the powders with better coatings features in biomedical metallic implants.

The first group of results allowed us to find and predict the APS thermal spray parameters that lead to obtaining high-quality coatings. The stand-off distance (SOD) was critical to get amorphous and highly bioactive coatings. On the contrary, the argon/hydrogen ratio did not change the coating efficiency or crystallization tendency. Current (I) changes with high SOD lead to obtaining thinner coatings compared to those obtain and low SOD. Finally, the cell viability results demonstrate that coated surfaces of TiAlV substrates showed higher viability compared to non-coated metallic surfaces. A similar analysis is expected to be obtained from the study and experimentations on the SGDP and EPD coating deposition techniques.

Keywords: Bioactive glass, Biocompatibility, Coatings, Medical Implants, Radiopacity.

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Biofabrication Using Alginate Dialdehyde, Gelatin, and Mesoporous Bioactive Glass Nanoparticle Composite Bioinks

Fatih Kurtuldu^{1,2}, Rainer Detsch², Martin Michálek¹, Dusan Galusek^{1,3}, and Aldo R. Boccaccini²

¹ FunGlass, A. Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

² Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

³ VILA – Join Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: fatih.kurtuldu@tuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

Bone tissue consists of three primary components: an organic matrix predominantly composed of collagen, an inorganic phase of calcium phosphates, and bone cells, including osteoblasts and osteoclasts. Recent advances in biofabrication have enabled the development of hybrid inorganic-organic materials that replicate bone composition; however, creating cell-laden bioinks to study the early stages of bone formation remains challenging. This study introduces a novel nanocomposite bioink comprising mesoporous bioactive glass nanoparticles (MBGNPs) with amine functional groups integrated into a hydrogel matrix of alginate di-aldehyde and gelatin. MBGNPs within the $\text{SiO}_2\text{-CaO-Ga}_2\text{O}_3$ system were synthesized via a microemulsion-assisted sol-gel method. Their structural and physicochemical properties were comprehensively characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and nitrogen adsorption-desorption analyses. The bioink was utilized to immobilize osteoblast (MC3T3-E1) and osteoclast (RAW 264.7) progenitor cells for extrusion-based 3D printing. The printed constructs demonstrated high cell viability, rapid cell spreading, and effective co-culture integration. Scaffolds were cultured in normal and osteogenic media to investigate osteoblast-osteoclast interactions after biofabrication process. Cell viability, alkaline phosphatase (ALP) expression, and morphology were assessed through SEM and fluorescence microscopy over 1, 3, 7, and 14 days. The findings emphasize the critical role of osteoblast-osteoclast interactions in bio-fabricating bone tissue and demonstrate the potential of co-culture systems in replicating the initial stages of bone co-culture development.

Keywords: bioactive glass, biofabrication, cell laden, gallium, mesoporous nanoparticles

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Preparation and investigation of hot corrosion, CMAS, and thermal shock behaviour of double-layer YSZ/LC+YSZ thermal barrier coatings

M. Parchovianský¹, Ariharan S.², A. Sekar¹, A.H. Pakseresht¹

¹Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, 911 50
Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: milan.parchoviansky@tnuni.sk)

² Materials and Mechanical Entity, Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Kerala, India

ABSTRACT

In this study, new double-layer YSZ/La₂Ce₂O₇ (LC)+YSZ coatings were developed using air plasma spraying (APS). The prepared coatings had a relatively smooth surface with melted and partially melted areas. Their resistance to hot corrosion, CaO-MgO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂ (CMAS) infiltration, and thermal shock were examined. YSZ was added to the upper layer to enhance the properties of lanthanum cerate (La₂Ce₂O₇, LC). During the hot corrosion tests, the corrosion salt reacted with the upper layer, leading to the identification of the CeO₂ phase and new corrosion products. The main phase identified was LaVO₄; the secondary phases were CeVO₄ and YVO₄. Additionally, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirmed the formation of new, cuboidal-shaped corrosion products. The infiltration of CMAS resulted in the formation of additional new products: Ca₄Mg_xAl₄Si_(6-x-γ)O₁₄ and Ca_{2.8}(La_xCe_{1-x}).₆(SiO₄)O_{6-4x}, with SEM showing CMAS infiltration through the upper layer in the form of islands. The thermal shock resistance tests indicated that the upper layer gradually peeled off, with the coating surviving 67 cycles. Possible failure mechanisms were identified, with failure attributed to the spallation of the upper layer from the surface layer by layer. After all tests, the top layer showed partial spalling and delamination, mainly due to the reaction of corrosive salt or CMAS with the top layer, resulting in changes in composition, crack formation, and the separation of part of the upper layer. Peeling of the upper layer through mainly horizontal cracks was observed after hot corrosion, CMAS, and thermal shocks. The NiCrAlY bond coat and YSZ interlayer remained undamaged.

Keywords: CMAS corrosion, hot corrosion, TBCs, thermal shock resistance

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Structural evolution and optical properties of SiO_x coating deposited using hollow cathode chemical vapor deposition

Omid Sharifahmadian¹, Kamalan Mosas¹, Ashokraja Chandrasekar¹, Y. Castro², A. Duran², Amirhossein Pakseresht¹ and Dušan Galusek^{1,3}

¹Department of Coating Process, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: kamalan.mosas@tnuni.sk)

²Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio, CSIC, Campus de Cantoblanco, 28049 Madrid, Spain

³Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia.

ABSTRACT

Silicon oxide (SiO_x) coatings are a promising alternative for improving the efficiency and lifetime of low-e and antireflective coated glasses. In this project, SiO_x coatings with various stoichiometries were deposited on glass substrates using hollow cathode plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (HC-PECVD). Compared to conventional PECVD techniques, HC-PECVD offers several benefits such as reduced film stress, improved uniformity and deposition rate of the film, and cost-effective manufacturing for industrial application. SiO_x coatings were deposited using two different precursors: silane (SiH₄) and 1,1,3,3-tetramethyldisiloxane (TMDSO). To determine the optimum process conditions for SiO_x coating, the variable process parameters such as reactive and precursor gas ratios, power, and deposition rate were changed. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), grazing incidence X-ray diffraction (GIXRD), and UV-Vis spectroscopy were used to study the surface chemistry and microstructure of the films. Topography and thickness of the films were assessed using a confocal microscope, ellipsometry, and profilometer. By adjusting the conveyor belt speed in a pilot line, the thickness and homogeneity of the films were optimized. The optimized process parameters for the deposition of silicon oxide coatings can be used to develop multilayer coatings for low-e and anti-reflection applications.

Keywords: Structural evolution, Silicon oxide, Thin films, Plasma, Optical properties.

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Process optimization for the deposition of TiO₂, TiN, and ZnO thin films via sputtering in a pilot scale

Kamalan Kirubaharan Amirtharaj Mosas¹, Omid Sharifahmadian¹, Ashokraja Chandrasekar¹, Y. Castro², A. Duran², A.H. Pakseresht¹ and Dušan Galusek^{1,3}

¹Department of Coating Process, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: kamalan.mosas@tnuni.sk)

²Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio, CSIC, Campus de Cantoblanco, 28049 Madrid, Spain

³Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia.

ABSTRACT

The process optimization in the sputtering process is necessary to achieve uniform thickness, film stoichiometry, and strong adhesion, which are crucial for enhancing the durability of thin films produced on a pilot scale. In our present study, the process parameters for producing stoichiometric ZnO from planar aluminum (2 wt.%) doped zinc oxide and 10Sn90Zn targets, as well as TiO₂ and TiN thin films from a titanium rotary target (99.9% purity), were optimized. The variable sputtering parameters, including power, reactive and sputtering gas ratios, deposition rates, and chamber working pressures, were systematically varied to identify the optimum process conditions for each thin film. The microstructure, surface chemistry, optical properties, and topographic features of the films were investigated by grazing incident X-ray diffraction (GIXRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), UV–VIS spectroscopy, profilometer, atomic force microscope (AFM), confocal microscope, and ellipsometry analysis. The process parameters were chosen based on the refractive index and film stoichiometry. The thickness of the films was optimized by varying the conveyer speed in a pilot line to ensure uniformity and repeatability. The optimized process conditions will be used to develop multilayer thin films for producing glasses with anti-reflective and UV filtering capabilities.

Keywords: Magnetron sputtering, ZnO thin films, Optical properties, TiO₂.

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Multifunctional Biodegradable Composite Coatings for Corrosion Control of Magnesium Alloys

Aatif Ijaz^{1*}, Emilia Merino², Amirhossein Pakseresht¹, Alicia Durán², Yolanda Castro², Dušan Galusek^{1,3}

¹Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

²Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio (ICV-CSIC), Campus de Cantoblanco, Madrid, Spain

³Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChPT STU, Trenčín, Slovakia

*E-mail: aatif.ijaz@tnuni.sk

ABSTRACT

Magnesium (Mg) is considered the lightest engineering material of the 21st century. The similarity of the mechanical properties of Mg alloys to those of human bones, along with their biocompatibility and biodegradability in biological systems, have established their applicability as bone implants. However, a high degradation rate accompanied by a large volume of hydrogen evolution and an increment of the pH causes premature fractures and wound-healing complications, which limit the clinical effectiveness of Mg-based implants. Functional composite coatings have been thus of great interest for enhancing the performance of Mg-based implants^{1,2}. In this work, we developed an optimized stimuli-responsive self-healing composite coating by adding polydopamine-coated chitosan-loaded mesoporous bioglass nanoparticles (PD@Chi@MBG) to a polyurethane (PU) matrix, which allows substantially slower degradation of Mg alloys upon coating damage due to the adsorption of PD and chitosan on a Mg substrate. The nanocomposite coatings were homogeneously coated on a Mg AZ31 alloy using a simple dip coating method at a controlled withdrawal rate. Scanning electron microscopy–energy-dispersive X-ray analysis, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, and thermogravimetric analysis were used to evaluate the surface morphology, composition, and distribution of PD@Chi@MBG in the PU matrix. Electrochemical and immersion tests were performed to investigate the biodegradation performance of AZ31 alloy with and without different surface coatings in simulated body fluids (SBF) at 37 °C. The nanocomposite-coated AZ31 Mg alloys exhibited a significantly lower degradation rate than the uncoated AZ31. These results suggest that biodegradable composite coatings have great potential for application in orthopedic implants.

Figure: Multifunctional biodegradable composite coating system and its working principle.

Keywords: Corrosion inhibitors; Corrosion monitoring; Corrosion protection; Nanocarriers; Self-healing coatings; Stimuli-responsive release.

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Exploring the combined effects of cerium-doped lanthanum magnesium hexaaluminate and surface roughness for superior CMAS protection in thermal barrier coatings

**Anusha Sekar¹, Milan Parchovianský¹, Dušan Galusek^{1,2}
and Amirhossein Pakseresht¹**

¹ Department of Coatings Process, Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass,
Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín
911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

² Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Alexander Dubcek University of
Trenčín, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(anusha.sekar@tuni.sk)

ABSTRACT

The combined impact of surface roughness and doping concentration on the spreading and infiltration characteristics of calcium magnesium aluminosilicate (CMAS) corrosion salts at high temperatures was investigated in this study. The study was conducted for different doping concentrations of Ce ($x=0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, \text{ and } 0.8$) and surface roughness levels, namely, $R_a= 0.5 \mu\text{m}, 1.5 \mu\text{m}, \text{ and } 2.5 \mu\text{m}$, on alternative topcoat material $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Ce}_x\text{MgAl}_{11}\text{O}_{19}$ bulk samples. Heat treatment was carried out at 1350°C for 2 h and 10 h. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM–EDS) were used for the analysis of the samples. The study indicated that the spreadability of molten CMAS increased with increasing surface roughness, with the lowest value occurring for the $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ sample and the highest value occurring for the $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ sample. Consequently, the lowest thickness of the infiltration layer was obtained for 20 wt.% cerium, which was approximately $27.2 \mu\text{m}$, 11% lower than that of the YSZ corroded by CMAS for just 2 h at 1250°C . The infiltration depth decreased with increasing doping concentration upto 40 wt.% cerium, after which it began to increase slightly, although it still remained lower than the conventionally used YSZ. To confirm the reaction products, CMAS and different doped samples were mixed at a ratio of 1:1 and subjected to similar thermal conditions to determine the different phase constituents formed. The reaction products were mainly composed of $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$, $\text{Ca}(\text{Mg},\text{Al})$, MgAl_2O_4 , CaSiO_3 and La-Ce apatite. The Ce-doped LHA bulks outperformed standard YSZ bulks in resisting CMAS infiltration at elevated temperatures ($>1250^\circ\text{C}$).

Keywords: Calcium magnesium aluminosilicate corrosion; Doping; High-temperature coatings; Spreadability; Thermal barrier coatings.

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Toward sustainable nuclear solutions: a dual approach to ^{137}Cs immobilization in waste management

Diana Lago¹, Jozef Kraxner¹, Dušan Galusek^{1, 2} and Enrico Bernardo³

¹ FunGlass – Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Slovakia.
(E-mail: diana.lago@tnuni.sk)

² Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChFT STU, Slovakia.

³ University of Padova, Department of Industrial Engineering, Italy.

ABSTRACT

In this talk, two approaches for immobilizing simulated nuclear waste will be presented, emphasizing the treatment of cesium, a particularly challenging element to stabilize. The first part will cover the alkali activation of discarded glass. In this case, an innovative method for cesium immobilization has been developed using alkali activation of pharmaceutical boro-alumino-silicate glass vials. Powdered glass is suspended in CsOH-based activating solutions and consolidated at near-room temperature (40°C), resulting in the formation of cementitious matrices through condensation reactions within the hydrated surface layers. This activation releases silicates, borates, and aluminates into the solution, which then interacts with Cs⁺ and NH₄⁺ ions and atmospheric CO₂, to produce phases with different chemical stability. The resulting blocks demonstrate high stability under boiling water, forming boro-pollucite (CsBSi₂O₆) as a stable, non-dissolvable phase. However, activation using pure CsOH can lead to cesium carbonate (CsHCO₃) formation, which dissolves upon boiling. A mixed CsOH-NH₄OH activation reduces the formation of cesium carbonate, thus enhancing cesium immobilization by integrating it more effectively into a stable matrix and limiting its solubility. This dual-alkali approach maximizes cesium retention, providing a promising sustainable radioactive waste management solution. Finally, a brief overview and preliminary results from ongoing research on 3D mono- and multi-material structures will be presented, focusing on glass materials designed for immobilizing hazardous metals.

Keywords: alkali-activation, boro-aluminosilicate glass vials, boro-pollucite, cold-consolidation, CsOH, CsOH-NH₄OH.

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Transforming Brown mud into a Catalyst for Sustainable Water Purification

Akansha Mehta^{1*}, Jozef Kraxner¹, Martin Schwentenwein², Dusan Galusek^{1,3}

¹FunGlass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, Studentska 2, 911 50 Trencin, Slovakia.

*E-mail: akansha.akansha@tuni.sk

²Lithoz GmbH Mollardgasse 85A/2/64–69, Vienna 1060, Austria.

³ Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

The Bauxite residue is a byproduct of the alumina refining process by the Bayers process. It is highly alkaline and rich in iron, aluminum, and other oxides, making it a potentially useful material in environmental applications, including water treatment. Recently, the potential utilizing practices of bauxite residue are in constructing industry and as a catalyst/membrane for water treatment [1-2]. The drawback hindering its maximum utilization is due to the alkalinity as well as low reactivity of the bauxite residue. Vitrification offers a promising method for stabilizing the hazardous components and transforming the material into a non-leachable and environmentally inert product. In this study, a waste mixture consists of brown mud with the addition of medical borosilicate glass was subjected for melting procedure at 1550°C to acquire waste derived glass (WDG), with the content of characteristic oxides; Fe₂O₃, SiO₂, CaO, Al₂O₃ and alkali oxides. The WDG was crushed, sieved, and used as a feedstock for the designing of different hierarchical 3D porous structure (gyroid, cubic, diamond and kagome) via LCM (Lithography based Ceramic Manufacturing) additive technique. To further utilize the 3D structures as membrane for photocatalysis, translucency property will play the crucial role, which is achieved by using multi-material printing. During the multi-material printing process, waste borosilicate glass material (BSG) is balanced on top and bottom layers for efficient light penetration and WDG is embedded inside the layers of BSG. Further, to increase the amount of α -Fe₂O₃/hematite phase in 3D structures, the structures were heat treated at 830°C, and the gyroid structure with the maximum mechanical strength of 6.35 MPa and 10% closed porosity was prepared. The hematite rich 3D printed structures were utilized for the photo Fenton degradation of phenols under visible light irradiation and the role of H₂O₂ addition is also discussed for the enhanced efficiency.

Keywords: bauxite residue, degradation of phenols, multi-material 3D printing, recovering hematite phase.

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Transforming waste glass into high-value products through digital innovation and sintering-aided additive manufacturing technology

A. Dasan¹, J. Kraxner¹, E. Bernardo², D. Galusek^{1,3}

¹FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

*email: arish.dasan@tnuni.sk

²Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

³Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

The accumulation of waste glass presents an environmental challenge, with millions of tons discarded annually due to limited recycling options and inefficiencies in traditional repurposing methods [1]. This study explores an innovative approach to transforming waste glass into high-value products by integrating digital advancements and sintering-aided additive manufacturing technology using binder jetting. This study demonstrates that by leveraging digital design tools and optimizing sintering parameters, waste glass can be transformed into customized, structurally integrated, and mechanically enhanced parts while minimizing resource consumption and waste. For this proof-of-concept study, waste fiberglass produced as a side product during the production process of E-glass by Johns Manville Slovakia a.s. was selected. The 3D printing process involved mixing glass powder (<125 µm) with an additive with different weight ratios, while a green-solvent-based liquid served as an ink, applied using a Voxeljet VX200 binder jetting printer. Samples produced using this approach had more than 95% dimensional accuracy. The green parts achieved compression (specimen size; LxHxW: 25x25x25 mm) and bending strength (60x15x15 mm) ranging from 0.3 to 1Mpa, depending on the orientation and other printing parameters. Meanwhile, the sintered parts exhibited strengths exceeding 50 MPa, irrespective of the orientation of the specimens. This approach demonstrates the potential for a wide range of applications, including architectural and construction, catalytic supports, and filters and membranes.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing- binder jetting; digital advancements; waste glass.

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Additive manufacturing of SOFC components by multi-material approach

A. Novokhatska¹, S. Nohut², J. Kraxner¹, M. Schwentenwein² and D. Galusek^{1,3}

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia
(E-mail: anastasiia.novokhatska@tnuni.sk)

² Lithoz GmbH, Vienna, Austria

³ Joint glass centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) is a promising electrochemical energy conversion device attracted much attention for its high conversion efficiency, environmental friendliness, and high fuel flexibility. However, due to the multilayer structure, the conventional manufacturing process of SOFCs involves lots of steps that are not only time-consuming and not reproducible, but the cost is extremely high. Moreover, considering harsh operating conditions, the performance degradation of SOFC systems occurs due to the delamination, cracking, or microstructural deterioration of the porous electrodes. The best performance solutions can be realized by preparing the monolithic structure of the stack using the multi-material approach in combination with 3D printing technology. This work aims to develop advanced ceramic composites in systems based on 8YSZ by the multi-material Lithography-based Ceramic Manufacturing (LCM) method. A multi-material approach was employed by dense 8YSZ layers between porous 8YSZ layers with different densification behaviour. The effect of pore-forming agent (PFA) content, layer thickness, and particle size distribution on the microstructure of 3D porous-dense structures sintered at 1450°C (3h) were studied. The 42-45 vol% 8YSZ slurries with 10-20 wt% PFA content and appropriate rheological properties were formulated. Different mono- and multi-material objects were printed by LCM printer CeraFab Multi 2M30 (Lithoz GmbH, Vienna, Austria). After sintering, the printed mono-material samples showed uniform densification and microstructure regardless of PFA content. Porosity measurements revealed that a total porosity of 49% with an open porosity of 20 % can be achieved by a PFA content of 15 wt% and a particle size distribution of 8YSZ powder in the range of 0.2-0.9 µm. This level of open porosity is sufficient for gas/fuel electrodes in SOFC systems [1]. The printed composites demonstrated uniform shrinkage across each layer, showing no defects between the dense and porous layers, regardless of the layer thickness or the content of PFA. These findings highlight the potential of multi-material 3D printing technology for preparing electrode-electrolyte composites for use in solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) applications.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing, Multi-material, SOFC, Yttria-stabilized zirconia.

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Cold consolidation of waste fiber glass: the role of alkalis and their concentration

P. Scanferla¹, H. Elsayed², J. Kraxner¹, E. Bernardo² and D. Galusek^{1,3}

¹ FunGlass – Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass. University of Trenčín, Trenčin, Slovakia
(E-mail: paolo.scanferla@tnuni.sk)

² Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

³VILA – Join Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Recycling, expressed as remelting and manufacturing of the original articles, is not fully applicable to many fractions of glass cullet. Thousands of tons of glass are still disposed of in landfills yearly. A solution is provided by alkali activation for the manufacturing of new components at nearly room temperature, starting from waste glass powders. This work deals with the analysis of microstructural changes in hardened suspensions of waste fiber glass in sodium or potassium hydroxide solutions. A minimum solution alkalinity threshold of 3 mol/L is required for the formation of a stable cementitious material, for both sodium and potassium activators. At the minimum molarity glass particles are mutually bonded by reactions involving thin surface layers. X-ray diffraction, infrared spectroscopy, and SEM investigations suggest the increasing formation of gel, from condensation reactions of dissolution products, with increasing alkalinity. The gel phase binds unreacted particles, forming denser samples. The mechanical strength of cold consolidated bodies is thus maximized with molarities from 7 to 11 mol/L, with mechanical strengths exceeding 45 MPa. The choice between alkali and activator molarity is a key factor in the application field of alkali-activated waste fiber glass. Recent findings suggest that NaOH suspensions facilitate a quicker setting of secondary phases, such as carbonates, which can be advantageous for direct ink writing of porous components with porosity levels reaching up to 40%. Conversely, KOH suspensions lead to a more extensive dissolution of glass, thereby enhancing gel formation and densification, typically resulting in a porosity that does not exceed 25%. This characteristic may make KOH suspensions particularly suitable for the production of blocks via binder jetting.

Keywords: Alkali activation, cold consolidation, porous ceramics, upcycling, waste fibre glass.

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Fabrication and Application of Porous Glass Microspheres Derived from Fiber Glass Waste

Mokhtar Mahmoud¹, Jozef Kraxner¹, Hamada Elsayed², Enrico Bernardo², Dušan Galusek^{1,3}

¹FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Trenčín, Slovakia.

Email: mokhtar.mahmoud@tnuni.sk

²Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Padova, Padova, Italy.

³Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChFT STU, Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

Additive manufacturing technology offers a promising avenue for advancing glass recycling practices, enabling the creation and functionalization of innovative products for diverse applications. This study presents a comprehensive approach involving upcycling fiberglass waste through a sequential process. Powdered glass fibers were converted into porous glass microspheres via alkali activation in a 9 M KOH solution and subsequent flame synthesis process. The masked stereolithography technique printed 3D scaffolds using porous glass microspheres. Following a de-binding process at 330 °C for 12 hours (heating rate 0.3 °C/min) and subsequent heating at 600 °C for 5 hours (heating rate 0.5 °C/min), the printed objects were sintered at 1000 °C (heating rate 10 °C/min) for 1 hour, resulting in a diamond cell structure with an open porosity of 90%. The bending strength of the 3D scaffold is 63 MPa. The highly porous 3D scaffold offers significant advantages for various applications, including water and air purification.

Keywords: glass waste, recycling, glass microspheres, stereolithography, 3d printing

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